

FEMINISM-MASCULISM, ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND PAY PERCEPTION AS PREDICTORS OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PUBLIC SECTOR WORKERS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception as predictors of job satisfaction among public employees in Anambra State, Nigeria. A total of 400 participants took part in the study, comprising 276 (61.4%) males and 124 (38.6%) females, aged between 24 and 70 years (mean age = 36.2, SD = 7.09). Convenience sampling was employed to select both participants and organizations. Three instruments were utilized: The Organizational Culture Scale, Pay Perception Questionnaire, and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. The research employed a cross-sectional and correlational design, utilizing Stepwise Multiple Linear Regression to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. The results indicated that feminism-masculism did not significantly predict job satisfaction, whereas organizational culture and pay perception were significant predictors. Collectively, feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception predicted job satisfaction. The study recommended the implementation of award programmes within organizational culture to recognize exceptional employee performance, thereby enhancing the atmosphere, work environment, and overall job satisfaction.

Keywords: Feminism-masculism, Organizational culture, Pay perception, Job satisfaction, Public employees.

Introduction

In the current climate of turbulent changes, organizations have begun to realize that employees represent their most valuable asset (Kirkland, 2019). Satisfied employees are imperative for contemporary business success and a key factor that separates thriving organizations from others. Looking at the rate of globalization and industrialization worldwide, there has been an unprecedented increase in the number and types of public organizations established to meet various needs (Cameron & Quinn, 2016). These include

organizations in sectors such as finance, telecommunications, and others. One of the critical factors enhancing the functionality of these organizations is their employees. Even in organizations reliant on operating machines, human oversight remains essential for guiding and optimizing operations.

High productivity and performance in most organizations are realized with the support and contributions of employees (Kirkland, 2019). This is because employees contribute to strategy development and the achievement of organizational goals. In this context, organizational culture and employee pay perception emerge as primary considerations for successful human resource management (Kirkland, 2019, Onyemaechi, 2025). A common belief is that the future of any enterprise depends on the quality of its workforce.

Feminism-Masculism, for this study, is defined as the social and cultural characteristics that distinguish women and men in society (Colman, 2013). Although women and men share similarities in many traits, their differences capture attention. Feminism-Masculism is virtually assessed in every study evaluating treatment, retention, and outcomes (Berrigan & Garfield, 2011). Gender expectations often influence behaviour; for example, women are perceived as agreeable to maintain social harmony, while men are considered more aggressive speakers (Poynton, 2015). These dynamics may affect workplace roles and perceptions of competence (Cakoft, 2015, Achebe, et.al 2023).

Organizational culture is a force that holds members together, influencing individual and organizational performance (Schein, 2019). While positive cultural values can enhance performance, their impact depends on alignment with employees' beliefs and values (Kristof-Brown et al., 2015). Value congruence, or the alignment between organizational values and individual beliefs, is associated with improved performance-related attitudes (Cameron & Nerina, 2009; Cameron & Quinn, 2016).

Martins (2022) highlighted the significance of subcultures, such as innovative, supportive, and bureaucratic cultures, in shaping organizational outcomes. Supportive and innovative cultures have been linked to higher employee satisfaction and productivity, while bureaucratic subcultures tend to correlate with lower satisfaction and performance. A neglect of subcultural dynamics may negatively impact overall organizational performance (Brian & Sutton, 2017, Okonkwo, et.al. 2023).

Pay perception, a psychological interpretation of compensation, is a critical component of human resources management (Kim, 2017). It influences job satisfaction, transfer decisions, absenteeism, and labor-management relations. Factors such as pay level, pay structure, and perceptions of fairness in distribution significantly shape pay satisfaction (Weiss et al., 2017; Tekleab et al., 2015). Dissatisfaction with pay can lead to negative emotional states, reduced job satisfaction, and lower organizational attractiveness.

Job satisfaction is closely tied to motivation, well-being, and productivity. Defined as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences (Locke, 1976), job satisfaction is essential for achieving recognition, promotion, and

fulfilment. It involves attitudes toward various aspects of work, including the nature of tasks, relationships with co-workers, and compensation (George, 2018). As a multifaceted concept, job satisfaction plays a pivotal role in efficiency and effectiveness within business environments (Aziri, 2018, Okonkwo, et.al, 2023).

Job satisfaction reflects an individual's perception that their job meets material and psychological needs. It serves as a foundation for employee engagement and organizational success, underscoring the importance of aligning workplace conditions with employee expectations (Mullins, 2015). Although many antecedents that affect a person's job satisfaction have been identified, as shown by the outcomes of several studies (Frye, 2020; Parisi & Weiner, 2019; Rentsch & Steel, 2012; Weiner, 2010), most of this research was conducted in Asian and European contexts, specifically in countries like the USA, Canada, China, India, and Australia. Research on this focus in Sub-Saharan Africa is relatively scarce (Olugbile, 2021). Therefore, studying job satisfaction while focusing on elements such as feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception as antecedents that shape an individual's experience within an organization is both timely and significant. This research aims to establish the predictive value of feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception on job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Job satisfaction is closely linked to productivity levels and the overall success of organizations. However, many organizations struggle to harness the factors that enhance employees' job satisfaction, resulting in minimal performance. Therefore, there is a need to investigate factors such as feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception to assess their predictive value on job satisfaction. Understanding whether factors like organizational culture and pay can shape employees' cognitive sense of satisfaction and positively influence their conduct could provide valuable insights to enhance organizational productivity.

Although numerous studies have explored feminism-masculism, organizational culture, pay perception, and job satisfaction, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has examined these variables simultaneously to capture their dynamics within public organizations in Anambra State. This gap is significant, given that the contributions of employees in both public and private sectors in Nigeria today play an essential role in the country's development. Hence the specific objectives of the study include;

1. To investigate if feminism-masculism will significantly predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.
2. To determine whether organizational culture will significantly predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.

3. To evaluate if pay perception will significantly predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

1. Feminism-masculism will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.
2. Organizational culture will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.
3. Pay perception will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Method

Participants

A total number of 400 employees were drawn from eight (8) public organizations in Anambra State, Nigeria, which include the Nnamdi Azikiwe University, National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), United Bank for Africa (UBA), Access bank, First bank, Zenith bank, Fidelity bank and Awka South Local Government Headquarter. They were selected using probability (cluster) non-probability sampling (convenience sampling technique), for the cluster, the participants were sampled from the different organization clusters. For the convenience, the participants were sampled based on the availability of the participants and their willingness to be part of the study. Convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of people easy to contact or to reach (Goodwin, 2013). There were 276 males (61.4%) and 124 females (38.6%). Participants ranged in age from 24 to 70 years ($M = 36.2$, $SD = 7.09$). 355 participants identified as Igbo ethnic group (75.7%), followed by 20 participants from Hausa/Fulani ethnic group (15.3%), 15 participants from Yoruba ethnic group (5.7%) and 10 others (3.3%) from other minority ethnic groups in the school. 355 participants identified as Christians (84.5%), 30 as Muslims (10.2%) and 15 identified as either traditionalists/pagan/others (5.0%)

Instruments

Three instruments were used in this study, namely: Organizational culture scale (OCS), Pay perception Questionnaire, Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ).

Organizational Culture Scale (OCS)

The Organizational Culture Scale (OCS) consists of 30 items, which has been developed by Kılıç (2006). The scale has cronbach alpha of 0.87 for the overall scale. The researcher using 50 employees from public organizations in Onitsha metropolis for a pilot study obtained the cronbach score of .80 for the overall scale. The instrument reported a convergent validity of .64 with the death anxiety scale. Participants will be asked to rate the degree to which they agree with each statement (on a Likert scale from 1- 5, with a score of 1 being “I strongly agree” and a score of 5 being “I strongly disagree”). Sample items included: “Our policies and procedures help us to provide the service our customers want and need.”; “People sometimes compromise company policies or principles to reach operational goals.”

Pay perception questionnaire (PSQ)

Pay perception Questionnaire” (PSQ), an 18- item instrument developed by Heneman& Schwab, (1985). The instrument was reported to demonstrate adequate reliability and dimensionality (Heneman&Scwhab, 1985; Judge &Welbourne, 1994). The instrument has a reliability Coefficient of .88, and Mogaji (2019) in his reliability and validity check in Nigeria reported an alpha score of 0.94 and a convergent validity score of 0.71. Respondents will be asked to indicate their degree of satisfaction with various aspects of pay on 5- point, “1 = Very Dissatisfied, 2 = Dissatisfied, 3 = Neither Dissatisfied nor Satisfied, 4 = Satisfied, 5 = Very Satisfied”.

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ-Short Form). Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ-short form) is a 20-item standardized scale and is especially designed to measure intrinsic and extrinsic job factors of employees. MSQ-short form was developed by Weiss, Dawis, England, and Lofquist (1967). MSQ-short form has 20 items which include; activity, responsibility, variety, social status, supervision of human relations, technical supervision, moral values, security, social service, authority, ability utilization, company policy, compensation, advancement, independence, creativity, working conditions, co-employees, recognition, and achievement. MSQ-short form is a 5-point Likert scale, responses of which range from 1 (very satisfied) to 5 (very dissatisfied). Reliability value of the scale is .77. The researcher using 50 employees from public organizations in Onitsha metropolis for a pilot study obtained the cronbach score of .82 for the scale. The instrument reported a convergent validity of .57 with the death anxiety scale.

Procedures

The researcher identified eight public organizations in Anambra State as the focus of the study. From each organization, 50 employees were selected, resulting in a total of 400 participants. Collaboration with public relations managers facilitated access to individual employees. Questionnaires were administered to willing staff members who met the inclusion criteria of being confirmed full-time employees. Staff who were reluctant or unwilling to participate were excluded from the study. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and no remuneration was provided to the participants. To ensure ethical compliance,

confidentiality and other ethical considerations, such as openness and informed consent, were adhered to throughout the research process. Participants were informed that the study was for research purposes only and that the findings would not be released in any way that could identify them individually.

Design and statistics

This study utilized a correlational research design, with data analysed in line with the hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance using stepwise multiple regression through SPSS version 25.0.

Results

Source: Questionnaire Primary Data

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics offeminism-masculism, organizational culture, pay perception, job satisfaction.

	N	Minimu m	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Age	400	24	70	36.2	7.09	.50	.126	-.91	.241
fem-mas	400	0	1	0.48	0.50	.17	.126	-2.00	.241
Organ. Culture	400	34	135	76.0	13.9	.94	.126	.77	.241
Pay Perception	400	20	82	43.2	9.12	.23	.126	.38	.241
Job satisfaction	400	24	93	48.8	9.71	.34	.126	.68	.241

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 provide a comprehensive overview of the variables under study: age, feminism-masculism, organizational culture, pay perception, and job satisfaction. These statistics highlighted the distribution, central tendencies, and variability of the data, offering valuable insights into the characteristics of the participants and their responses. The sample comprised 400 participants with ages ranging from 24 to 70 years. The mean age of 36.2 years indicates that the average respondent is in their mid-thirties, reflecting a relatively young and active workforce. The standard deviation of 7.09 suggests moderate variability in the age distribution, indicating a reasonably diverse sample

in terms of age. The skewness value of 0.50 shows a slight positive skew, meaning there are slightly younger participants compared to the average age. Furthermore, the kurtosis value of -0.91 points to a flatter-than-normal age distribution, suggesting that age is spread out more evenly across the sample. For the feminism-masculism variable, the data is binary, with values of 0 and 1, representing two distinct categories. The mean score of 0.48 reflects an almost equal distribution between the categories. The standard deviation of 0.50 aligns with the binary nature of the data. The skewness of 0.17 indicates a nearly symmetrical distribution, while the kurtosis of -2.00 suggests a platykurtic distribution, indicating less clustering around the mean and a flatter overall shape. Organizational culture scores range from 34 to 135, with a mean of 76.0. This suggests a moderately positive perception of organizational culture among the participants. The standard deviation of 13.9 demonstrates considerable variability, indicating differing levels of perception regarding organizational culture within the sample. The skewness of 0.94 reveals a moderate positive skew, with some participants rating organizational culture higher than the mean, while the kurtosis value of 0.77 suggests a slightly more peaked distribution compared to the normal curve. Pay perception, another critical variable, has scores ranging from 20 to 82, with a mean of 43.2. This reflects a moderate level of satisfaction with pay among the respondents. The standard deviation of 9.12 indicates variability in perceptions of pay satisfaction, suggesting diverse views among participants. The skewness value of 0.23 reveals an almost symmetrical distribution, and the kurtosis value of 0.38 shows a slightly flatter-than-normal distribution, indicating that responses are fairly evenly spread. Finally, job satisfaction scores range from 24 to 93, with a mean score of 48.8, suggesting moderate levels of job satisfaction among the participants. The standard deviation of 9.71 shows variability in job satisfaction levels across the sample.

Table 2: Zero Order Matrix Correlational Co-Efficient Statistics of Feminism-masculism, Organizational culture, Pay perception and Job satisfaction

	AGE	F-M	ETH	REL	OC	PP	JS
AGE	1.00						
F-M	-.074	1.00					
ETH	-.087*	.052	1.00				
REL	.078	-.112*	-.134*	1.00			
OC	.121*	-.160*	.270**	-.31**	1.00		
PP	.003	-.141*	-.008	.134*	.390**	1.00	
JS	-.170*	.003	.181*	-.191*	-.140*	.220**	1.00

The results in table 2 indicated that there is negative significant relationship between age = -.17*, religion = -.19*, organizational culture = -.14*, at $r(N=400)$, $p < .05$. Conversely,

ethnicity= .18*, pay perception = .22** had significant relationship with job satisfaction at $r(N=400)$, $p<.05$. On the other hand, feminism-masculism had no significant relationship with job satisfaction at $r(N=400)$, .003, $p>.05$.

Table 3: Stepwise Linear Regression Statistics of Feminism-masculism, organizational culture and pay perception on Job satisfaction

Sources	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. E.E	F	Df	B	T	Sig.
Step 1	.591	.585	.579	8.540	8.125	4			
Age							.071	1.660	.070
Fem-Mas							.045	1.121	.082
Step 2	.509	.495	.489	8.631	4.785	5			
Age							.246	5.624	.000
Fem-Mas							.052	1.321	.135
Organizational Culture							.240	3.100	.041
Step 3	.511	.501	.494	8.239	10.268	6			
Age							.153	4.126	.000
Fem-Mas							.043	1.163	.231
Organizational culture							.024	2.544	.038
Pay perception							.512	2.379	.018

Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

The step 1 results in Table 3 showed that demographic factors (age, feminism-masculism) accounted for 59.1% of the job satisfaction, with $R = .591$, $R^2 = .585$, adjusted $R^2 = .579$, $(F4, 395) = 8.125$, $p<.05$. This showed that the overall step 1 has significant contribution to job satisfaction at 59.1%. The step 2 results showed that demographic factors (age, feminism-masculism) and organizational culture accounted for 50.9% of the job satisfaction, with $R = .509$, $R^2 = .495$, adjusted $R^2 = .489$, $(F5, 394) = 4.785$, $p<.05$. This showed that the overall step 2 has significant contribution to job satisfaction at 50.9%. The step 3 results showed that demographic factors (age, feminism-masculism), organizational culture and pay perception accounted for 51.1% of the job satisfaction, with $R = .511$, $R^2 = .501$, adjusted $R^2 = .494$, $(F6, 393) = 10.268$, $p<.05$. This showed that the overall step 3 has significant contribution to job satisfaction at 51.1%. Organizational culture at $(F5, 394)$, $\beta = .24^{**}$, $p<.05$, and pay perception at $(F6, 393)$, $\beta = .51^{**}$, $p<.05$ had significant prediction on job satisfaction.

Discussion

Based on the study findings, first hypothesis which stated that Feminism-masculism will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria was accepted, because from the study finding, feminism-masculism showed to be a non-significant predictor of Job satisfaction among employees in Anambra state. This result agrees with Nsaful et al., (2021) who found that feminism-masculism and work-family conflict were not significantly related to job satisfaction; and feminism-masculism also did

not moderate the relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction. Also, HohyunSong (2020) found feminism-masculism stereotypes to have no effect on job satisfaction. Conversely, Klassen and Chiu (2020) found in their study that feminism-masculism influenced the Job satisfaction of the employees in the IT area, reporting that women who work as information technology professionals are less satisfied than male colleagues with their compensation and promotion opportunities. Looking at the Two-factor theory by Herzberg (1959) which states that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction is a product of different factors – motivation and hygiene respectively. Motivation is seen as an inner force that drives individuals to attain personal and organizational goals. Motivational factors are those aspects of the job that make people want to perform and provide people with satisfaction. Hygiene factors include aspects of the working environment like working conditions, interpersonal matters, organizational policies and so on, which explains why feminism-masculism in this study did not predict job satisfaction among organizational employees in Anambra State because feminism-masculism are either a motivational construct for an employee nor a hygienic factor as specified by the two-factor theory.

Second hypothesis which stated that Organizational culture will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria was not accepted because from the finding of this study, Organizational culture significantly predicted job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra State. This is in line with the findings of Tsai (2022) who examined the relationship between organizational cultures, leadership behaviour and job satisfaction of employees, and reported that organizational cultures were significantly (positively) correlated with job satisfaction. This finding show that culture within an organization is very important, playing a large role in whether it is a happy and healthy environment in which to work. In communicating and promoting the organizational ethos to employees, their acknowledgement and acceptance of it can influence their work behaviour and attitudes. When the interaction between the leadership and employees is good, the latter will make a greater contribution to team communication and collaboration, and will also be encouraged to accomplish the mission and objectives assigned by the organization, thereby enhancing job satisfaction. Also the study was consistent with the findings of Soryani, Syah and Pujo (2020) who investigated the influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction to the employees and reported that organizational culture had an influence on job satisfaction. This appears so because the strongest indicator that formed the organizational culture was the comfortable feeling of all employees to the appreciation and positive cultures that can provide space for them to work optimally.

Third hypothesis which stated that pay perception will not predict job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra state, Nigeria was rejected. This was because Pay perception significantly predicted job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra State. This finding is in line with the result of Serreqi (2020), who reported the influence of pay perception on job satisfaction based on his findings. With respect to the influence of the dimensions of pay perception there are significant relationships between pay

level, pay raises and benefits with citizenship behaviour directed at individuals or employees with high job satisfaction. However, the finding of this study antagonizes the findings of Ezeh and Olawale (2021) who investigated the relationship between pay perception and job satisfaction among Federal Civil Servants, and found that pay perception had no significant relationship with job satisfaction and turnover intention. Vroom (1964) in his expectancy theory contended that the strength of a tendency to act in a certain way is a function of the strength of an expectation that the action would lead to a specific outcome. This theory succinctly explain why some employees would not engage in extra efforts on their job, but only do the minimum necessary to get by since they are aware that they would not get rewarded for such extra effort, which further explains why pay perception significantly predicted job satisfaction among public organization workers in Anambra State.

Conclusion

This study examined feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception as predictors of job satisfaction among public organization employees in Anambra State, Nigeria. The results revealed that feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception are significant predictors of employees' job satisfaction. It is concluded that both employees and organizational employers should recognize and address pay-related issues, discrepancies in organizational culture, and gender inequalities among staff. Addressing these factors is crucial for minimizing their adverse effects on employees' job satisfaction and enhancing overall performance and productivity. When these challenges are effectively tackled, the relationship between organizations and their employees is likely to improve, fostering a positive perception of the organization and encouraging greater cooperation. Based on the findings, persistent job dissatisfaction among employees need not continue. With targeted improvements in organizational culture, pay structures, and incentives, the work environment can be significantly enhanced, benefiting both employees and the organizations they serve.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered;

The first recommendation is fostering cohesion among leaders and employees through social events, outings, and team-building gatherings, which promote a positive culture and atmosphere. These activities help build camaraderie, teamwork, and a sense of value among employees. Establishing a supportive and inclusive atmosphere improves the organizational environment and enhances the overall work experience.

The second recommendation is implementing an awards program within the organizational culture to recognize employees who perform their work exceptionally. Such a program can significantly improve and positively influence the organizational atmosphere and work environment, fostering motivation and appreciation among staff.

Third, organizations and management that are receptive to employees' concerns (e.g., pay perception) can adopt strategies to maintain a high level of employee engagement and satisfaction. Providing opportunities for employees to participate in decision-making processes helps address uncertainties and allows them to remain competitive and perform effectively, especially during complex and uncertain times.

Finally, adopting a flexible leadership approach, or liquid leadership, allows leaders to adapt their interactions to suit individual employees. This leadership style enables organizations to identify the best strategies for improving person-organization fit, placing employees in roles where they can succeed, stay motivated, and feel satisfied. Additionally, liquid leadership fosters open communication, making employees at all levels feel comfortable voicing their concerns and ideas, which builds trust and confidence in leadership. This approach aligns with effective leadership and constructive feedback, ultimately contributing to employee satisfaction and organizational success.

Limitations of the Study

The current study encountered several limitations that may have influenced the results. Firstly, the sample was drawn from only eight public organizations in Anambra State, which limits the generalizability of the findings to the entire population of workers in the region. Additionally, this study focused solely on feminism-masculism, organizational culture, and pay perception, while other important variables, such as job characteristics and job security, may also impact job satisfaction. Furthermore, the study utilized only a quantitative method; future research would benefit from employing a mixed-methods approach (triangulation) to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing job satisfaction. In conclusion, job dissatisfaction and poor organizational commitment remain significant challenges in Nigeria, which should be addressed to prevent low levels of productivity among employees.

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